

Nano Imprint Lithography

A green technology

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Abstract

In the 3-week term June 2010 we have worked with Nano Imprint Lithography (NIL) in the course Nanolithography. NIL is a nonconventional lithographic technique for high-throughput patterning of polymer nanostructures at great precision and at low costs. NIL relies on direct mechanical deformation of the resist material and can therefore achieve resolutions beyond the limitations set by light diffraction or beam scattering that are encountered in conventional techniques.

In this presentation we will present NIL as an energy efficient and environmental friendly technology compared to traditional micro and nano fabrication approaches. We will introduce NIL and describe why it can be considered a green technology.

Nano Lithography in short

Lithography (greek word meaning "to write in stone") is a process used to create patterns in (mostly silicon) substrates. The process was created and developed by IBM in the 60's to make integrated circuits that are now used everywhere in everyday life, found in all electronics. The process involves a series of chemical and physical steps, all requiring high cleanliness, good control of involved processes and high requirements on precision. While processor speed, bits/area and such are getting faster and higher, the physical feature size is getting smaller, this also means the processes are getting refined and the control of variation, positions and so on must improve at the same rate. Today energy consumption is not prioritized in the semiconductor industry, but in the more and more environmentally conscious world it is a factor that must be considered. Low energy consumption is also a factor in making NIL commercially profitable.

We now compare NIL to two alternatives, E-beam Lithography and Ultra Violet Lithography. In the process descriptions we only consider the steps important for energy consumption and the steps important for understanding the process.

Nano structures

The picture shows a Scanning Electron Microscope image of a photonic crystal in a Liquid Crystal Laser. The picture was taken in the Danchip cleanroom during the 3-week term June 2010 Nanolithography course. The structures in the crystal are about 190 nm long and 130 nm wide.

Nano Imprint Lithography

NIL is a method for transferring designs to a polymer resist, for further development, done by heating the resist and physically imprint a structure in the molden polymer, using a stamp containing the negative image of the structure. E-beam lithography is used to make the stamp, which then can be used for many imprints.

E-beam Lithography

E-beam lithography (EBL), unlike the two other forms of lithography, does not need a mask but directly writes the pattern in the resist by accelerating electrons to high velocities and focusing the beam in a very small spot that is moved around on the resist. This changes the property of the exposed areas of the resist that can now be chemically removed without affecting the non-exposed areas.

Ultra Violet Lithography

Ultraviolet lithography (UVL) is a process where ultraviolet light is exposing a resist by shining through holes in a mask, thus changing exposed areas of a resist to either be more or less soluble. A pattern can in this way be created by chemical development after the exposure.

Process steps and energy consumption of Nano Imprint Lithography^[1]

See EBL in the middle table

- Stamp production by e-beam lithography.
- Energy consumption for this is very high.
- However this is only done once, and if the stamp is used many times, the energy consumption per imprint becomes rather small.

- Polymer deposition. Polymer is spun on a silicon wafer.

- Heating of polymer.
- The polymer is heated to increase viscosity. The temperature is approx. 100-200°C.
- The air must also be purified and the pressure lowered to low vacuum..
- Energy for the low vacuum in approx. 20 minutes: **2kW · 20 min = 0,7 kWh**

- Thermoplastic squeeze flow.
- The stamp is placed in the viscous polymer and a certain pressure is applied to the stamp to squeeze the resist into the cavities of the stamp.

- The polymer is cooled and thereby hardens. The stamp can be removed.

- The residual polymer layer is etched, typically with a Reactive Ion Etch (RIE).
- RIE is done in high vacuum so the energy consumption is not negligible.
- Energy for the high vacuum in approx. 5 minutes: **20kW · 5 min = 2 kWh**

Process steps and energy consumption for E-beam Lithography^[2]

- Electron sensitive Resists applied, often with a thin metal film on top.

- The resist is exposed point by point, from an electron gun.
- The very high vacuum has to be maintained during the entire exposure that can easily take a day for a normal wafer. A lot of energy is needed for the high vacuum and temperature control:

$$24 \text{ h} \cdot 130 \text{ kW} = 3000 \text{ kWh}$$

- The electron beam itself also consumes some energy, but it's quite little compared to the energy for the vacuum and temperature.

- Resist that has been exposed will now be removed by the chemical developer. If a metal film is present it is removed prior to the exposure.

Conclusion

We compared the energy consumption for the three different lithography methods. The estimated energy consumptions per wafer are:

- NIL: 2 kWh
- EBL: 3000 kWh
- UVL: 17 kWh

According to these estimates NIL definitely appears to be the most environmentally friendly technology, while direct E-beam lithography uses vast amounts of energy. Another advantage about NIL is that it does not use any developer chemicals, contrary to both EBL and UVL.

Process steps and energy consumption in Ultra Violet Lithography^[3]

- Masks can be created by several different ways (depending on the features size), but one of the most common and accurate methods is using an electron beam to etch a desired pattern. Energy consumption is very high.

- Masks are used many times, thus the energy consumption per silicon wafer becomes rather small.

- Photoresist coating. Polymer is spun on a silicon wafer.

- The photoresist, surface, and mask are subjected to UV light via a UV lamp of polymer.

- The pressure lowered to high vacuum.

- Energy for the high vacuum in approx. 10 minutes: **100kW · 10 min = 17 kWh**

- Energy for Xenon exposure in approx. 1 minute: **9kW · 1 min = 0.2 kWh**

- Exposed photoresist removed by developer.

- Chemicals are applied to the surface causing either a positive photoresist reaction or a negative photoresist reaction.

- This causes usage of chemicals.

References:

- [1] A. Kristensen 33422 Handouts. [2] May, Sze *Fundamentals of Semiconductor Fabrication*, 2004 Wiley. [3] M. J. Madou, *Fundamentals of Microfabrication*, 2002 CRC Press.